

**A STUDY ON ONLINE BLENDED MODE OF LEARNING SYSTEM IN
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AT COLLEGE LEVEL
IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT**

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Abstract :

Newline In the sphere of education, e-learning technologies constitute a significant advancement. With the introduction of e-learning and communication newline technology in India, the newline educational sector has undergone a transformation Coimbatore district newline explores the engagement of e-learning and improvement activities for students in a newline study on e-learning systems in educational institutions at the college level. Newline The purpose of this study is to identify characteristics that influence student motivation, attitude toward newline e-learning, and the necessity for faculty to use e-learning methods in managing the environment at newline educational institutions. Newline This study examines students' e-learning challenges and offers newline suggestions for improving e-learning in educational institutions. Faculty members chose from a variety of e-learning strategies to improve learning in the classroom.

Key words: *New line E-Learning, Students motivation to E-Learning.*

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Introduction :

In recent years, India's educational system has achieved considerable strides. India is the world's most fascinating educational market. In India, education is undergoing significant changes. Education is a never-ending process of improvement. It is about an ever-expanding man in an ever-expanding society. In India, there are about 60 million persons under the age of 25. There is a lot of demand on the system to expand. Because India's young population has such a strong desire for education, and as the middle class grows, millions of people will be able to afford it. Instead of becoming the low-quality service provider nation that we are becoming, the purpose of our new education system should be to produce entrepreneurs, inventors, artists, scientists, thinkers, and writers who can build the foundation of a knowledge-based economy.

Objective :

To determine the factors that influence student motivation in e-learning as well as management effectiveness.

Review of Literature :

E-learning Efficiency Fischer.H (2018) conducted study how dealings of scientific conferences can be used for education in the field of e-learning. They described the abstracts of 427 scientific articles of leading German-speaking e-learning conferences. The study was carried out at German-speaking conferences and, thus, reflects the situation in Germany, 67 Switzerland and Austria. These studies pointed out an important contribution to the diffusion of digital media in higher education. The researchers discovered that the detailed analysis of the frequency distribution over the seven years reflects the intensity of scientific discussion towards e-learning latest trends in institutions, and conclusions about digital potentials of innovations can be introduced. Especially, they identified the development potential of learning management, mobile learning, virtual worlds, e-portfolio, and social media. Massive Open Online Courses are crucial for e-learning in educational institutions at Germany.

Richard and Haya (2015) identified the internet has opened new potential and now one type of learning content. It may be for school, graduate or masters level, employee training, research activity or any other type of academic offering is called e-learning. E-Learning has already started its records and its popularity can be estimate from the fact that delivery is not restricted to just plain text but has crossed limits to video creating virtual class rooms via video conferencing. The introduction of a different of technologies has made it possible to exchange it from impersonal to highly interactive medium of pedagogy (the art and science of teaching). The Internet has become one of the vital ways to make available resources for research and learning for both staffs and students to share and obtain information. Technology based e-learning covers the utilize of the internet and other significant technologies to construct materials for learning, teach students, and also standardize courses in an institution.

Research Methodology :

Primary data was acquired from the various departments and students of the Coimbatore district's Arts and Sciences College. It was a fantastic opportunity for the resource to meet the respondents one-on-one and collect data quickly using a well-structured set of questions. The survey was conducted at the institution by making a previous appointment with the respondents at a time that was convenient for them.. Secondary data have been collected from various sources namely from journals, magazines, other research work and also from other authentication websites.

Analysis and Interpretation :

A Rank Order Scale gives the respondent a set of items and asks them to put the items in some form of order. The measure of 'order' can include such as preference, importance, liking, effectiveness and so on. Rank Order Scale is also known as Raking Scale. In surveys, the most commonly used question types are ranking scale questions. This is where respondents are asked to indicate their personal levels on things such as agreement, satisfaction or frequency. Ranking scale questions are best used when you want to measure your respondent's attitude toward something

Table no 1
The Factors Influence on Motivation in Factor Analysis

S.NO	FACTORS	11	10	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	TOTAL	MEAN
	Factor: 1 Encouraging learning Environment													
	Faculty encourages there to daily use of internet	6	5	4	6	7	9	8	4	3	3	0	55	6.8
	An institution stimulates increasing more effective for adapting technology to support e-learning infrastructure.	66	50	36	48	49	54	40	16	9	6	0	374	
2	Factor:2 Teaching & Learning Process													
	Stimulate and cheerful virtual classroom environment	5	10	6	4	3	5	5	5	1	6	5	55	6.5
	Combining of teaching/learning in class with video conferencing.	55	100	54	32	21	30	25	20	3	12	5	357	
3	Factor:3 Content Effectiveness													
	Shorter notes that focuses on what really need to learn	4	4	9	8	6	4	3	3	4	6	4	55	6.4
	Multimedia presentations stimulated interest. (e.g., graphics, audios, videos)	44	40	81	64	42	24	15	12	12	12	4	350	

4	Factor:4 Participation & Attention													
	Providing more extra points for a university course because of participation in e-learning	8	3	4	4	4	8	3	10	7	3	1	55	6.3
	Encouraging constant to produce new ideas	88	30	36	32	28	48	15	40	21	6	1	345	
	Factor:5 Preference													
6	Deliver content in the right format	9	2	9	4	5	2	5	2	2	7	8	55	6.2
	Encouragable delivery content to learn	99	20	81	32	35	12	25	8	6	14	8	340	

Source: Primary Data

Findings :

The factors that influence student motivation were discovered. By grouping the linked variables under it, it was shown that there are five important components that influence student motivation. These are: Encouraging learning environment (Rank I), Teaching & Learning process (Rank II), Content Effectiveness (Rank III), Participation & Attention, Stimulate skills (Rank IV), Preference (Rank V).

Suggestions :

The main constraints for faculty will be required to attend e-teaching seminars or conferences, and e-learning experts will be invited to give speeches and demonstrations in order to improve faculty capacities and share experiences. The faculty will have a better understanding of their attitudes and motives for implementing e-learning in their schools. We believe that by doing so, we will be able to detect the importance of students' shifting behaviour throughout the course of the study. Advances in internet technology, particularly in wireless bandwidth internet connections, will have a significant impact on motivation for more online learning and interactive lessons to be delivered and followed.

Conclusion :

Finally the results of this investigation will be simplified with caution and after careful consideration of all factors. It is envisaged that if the aforementioned ideas are implemented in the Coimbatore district, more students will be influenced to use e-learning. Students in arts & science colleges focus on a variety of learning methods. The use of e-learning in educational institutions is now on the rise. To a significant extent, it will succeed.

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Cite This Article:

P. Jeyamathi, (2022). A study on online blended mode of learning system in educational institutions at college level in coimbatore district. Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal, XI (II), 268-272